

Investigating Missing Citations in COCI and the Publishers Involved

Alessia Cioffi¹, Sara Coppini¹, Arianna Moretti¹ and Nooshin Shahidzadeh Asadi¹

¹ {alessia.cioffi, sara.coppini, arianna.moretti2, noo.shahidzadehasadi}@studio.unibo.it

Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies,
University of Bologna, via Zamboni 32, 40126 Bologna (Italy)

Abstract

Purpose

The primary purpose of this research is to find the publishers responsible for the missing citations in COCI (the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations) by sending incorrect metadata to Crossref, the publishers to whom such invalid citations point to, and the number of previously invalid citations which are currently valid. Further, the additional aim of the present research is to provide material for future and deeper research on the same subject matter. In particular, we focus on keeping track of the main trends of evolution on the validity of citational data and on providing data to facilitate publishers' identification.

Study design/methodology

In order to study the invalid citations, we use an already generated CSV file which is available online, containing - for each citation - the valid citing DOI and the invalid cited DOI. First of all, through a DOI API request we check whether the validity state of the cited DOI has changed, and then we use DOI's prefix for a Crossref API request, in order to identify the responsible and referenced publishers.

Findings

For each individual publisher, we retrieve the number of incorrect citations metadata sent, and the number of invalid citations received, to which we decided to add the information about the number of addressed and received citations validated with the software we developed, and its list of prefixes. We also extract the total number of invalid citations that have since been corrected. Any further material provided as result of this research, such as the lists of validated and still invalid citations, is meant to incentivize future improvements of the studies in this field.

Originality/value

The results of this research may point us to publishers who generally send out incorrect citation metadata and, inversely, those who generally receive invalid citations. These findings can first of all raise awareness of the accuracy of certain publishing houses in managing their metadata (or lack thereof). Moreover, finding these trends and showcasing

the labor of the corrections may lead to increasingly valid citations if the proper measures are taken.

Research limitations/implications

Based on the available data for COCI, there may be a slight bias in our sample, causing some publishers to be incorrectly represented.

1. Introduction

Citations are one of the fundamental aspects of scientific research. Citing someone else's work means, above all, acknowledging the work made by others, showing the provenance and affirming the reliability of the data by recalling a previous research in the work. This is the reason why it is so important to deal with open citations, which means that citations are “freely accessible and reusable” (<https://i4oc.org/>). OpenCitations (OC, <https://opencitations.net/>) is “a scholarly infrastructure organization dedicated to open scholarship and the publication of open bibliographic and citation data” (Peroni & Shotton, 2020). Founding member of the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC), it represents a relevant project inside the Open Science domain, in particular for what concerns the open scholarly citations. Indeed, its capability of conveying a relevant number of (open) citational information allows the creation of a wide net for the scientific community. COCI (<https://opencitations.net/index/coci>) is the OC's Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations. It is an RDF dataset containing the details of all the citations that are specified by the open references to DOI-identified works present in Crossref (<https://www.crossref.org/>), as of the latest COCI update. It was first created in 2018, and up to now it contains 759.5 millions of citations and 60.7 millions of bibliographic resources.

All the information collected by OpenCitations and stored in COCI comes from Crossref, a not-for-profit association for reference linking through Digital Object Identifiers. However, not all Crossref citations are transferred in COCI: some of them because of ethical reasons, i.e. because they are not open or they are not provided with a DOI, but some others are not inserted because of the invalidity of the DOI held by the cited entity. But while the first type of omission is voluntary, the second one is due to technical errors. Hence, it represents a loss of information not only for OpenCitations but also for the scientific community. Moreover, also the publishers of the article connected to these invalid identifiers are directly affected by this gap from two different perspectives:

- they can be, more or less consciously, the direct responsables for committing the errors which invalidate the DOIs of the cited source. Indeed since Crossref does not provide a double-check of the information provided by the publishers, before the creation of the DOI of the resources, if the publishers commit an error then, as consequence, the DOI will result to be wrong, and therefore invalid;
- they can be the publishers of the articles which are wrongly cited and, because of this, they lose all the advantages of being citable (e.g. acknowledgments).

Therefore, investigating the connection of the invalid DOIs with the corresponding publishers can be a key in order to better contextualize the problem and try to fix it.

There are some similar works, either projects or researchers, which have inspired the actions we carried out in the development of this project. The first one is “Crowdsourcing open citations with CROCI An analysis of the current status of open citations, and a proposal” by Heibi, Peroni and Shotton (Heibi, Peroni, & Shotton, 2019). This one is the most similar to the first step of our research: retrieving the publishers of the correct citing articles and of the wrong cited articles, only knowing the DOIs of the publications. In the aforementioned work, the most relevant aspect to our research is the way in which the authors retrieve the publishers from their DOIs: “querying the Crossref API using the entity's DOI prefix”, which has then become our method of working. Other works (Boudry & Chartron, 2017; Franceschini et al., 2015; Heibi, Peroni, & Shotton, 2019) allowed for a wider contextualisation of the topic, either describing the numeric composition of the DOIs or the common mistakes made by publishers with respect to the DOIs.

The purpose of this work derives from the research questions that have guided it from the very beginning. At the outset of the project, the research questions that were defined

concerned the identification of the publishers responsible (due to their incorrect metadata sent to Crossref) for the missing citations in COCI; the identification of the publishers to which such invalid citations point (i.e. who published the cited articles); and the number of currently valid citations among those initially invalid according to our input data. However, during the development of the project, the need emerged to retrieve additional information by enriching the initial research questions. In particular, the data obtained and collected in the output file are the following:

- the names and identifiers of the publishers involved in the citations (either as the publishers of the citing DOI or the publisher of the cited DOIs);
- the numbers of the valid and invalid citations they are responsible for as the publishers of the valid citing DOI;
- the number of the valid and invalid citations they are involved in as publishers of the cited DOI;
- the list of still invalid citations;
- the list of now valid citations.

The reasons behind the inclusion of this specific kind of data are both practical and theoretical, but always with the aim of increasing the quality of the results. In the first place, we wanted to track the evolutions in the citations' state, from invalid to valid or still invalid, so as to make comparisons and compute ratios. Furthermore, we assumed that associating with each publisher the total numbers of missing citations in which it is involved and those for which it is responsible — rather than merely retrieving the names of the publishers linked somehow to the citing or cited DOI — could allow us to identify patterns or make comparisons among publishers, in order to identify the most responsible ones (i.e. publishers of cited publications with valid DOI) or most involved (i.e. publishers of cited publications with invalid DOI). In the second place, instead of reporting only the total number of now valid citations, having each validated citational data in an ordered structure facilitate an eventual integration in COCI of now valid citations; while having still invalid citational data in an ordered structure allow for their exportation and reuse for further studies on missing citations. Finally, this additional information allows us to generate more complex and structured data visualizations, to represent different kinds of results in a clear way and to aid the interpretation of the data.

Based on the research questions and hence on the purpose of the project thus defined, the objective of our work is firstly to identify the main publishers involved in these missing citations; and, secondly, patterns of errors and if they could be attributable to certain activities of some publishers; for instance, if the presence of these incorrect DOIs is to attribute exclusively to the incorrect sending of the citational metadata of the publications by the publisher to Crossref. This objective could be translated into another broader objective within the more general research area in which the COCI and OpenCitations projects are located, as well as the other projects that deal with open citational data. As mentioned, this further development could be to make sure that more data can be integrated into COCI by grasping the issue of invalid DOIs at the root, therefore not correcting the invalid DOIs already collected, but correcting the activities carried out by the publishers that lead to these missing citations and invalid data; or hypothesize a different method of collecting the citational data from publishers that can prevent the insertion of incorrect citational data in platforms such as Crossref.

Starting from this disciplinary area and from the objectives set with the research questions, an open working methodology was outlined that respected the FAIR principles, from processing collected input data to processing final data, from the use of platforms and tools open access and open non-proprietary formats to store data, as explained in Section 2; where the main structure of the code is also presented. This methodology has led us to obtain consistent and significant results - especially in the comparison between the data concerning the publishers of resources with cited DOIs and the publishers of resources with cited DOIs - of which we illustrate the most important points in Section 3. However, the interpretation of the data and the discussion of the results obtained, their significance and implication in this research area has been reserved for Section 4. Finally, Section 5 is devoted to a brief conclusion on the research work carried out within this project, where we summarize the answers to the research questions and propose some possible scientific implications of the work and potential further developments.

2. Materials and methods

To answer the research questions mentioned above, we used open data and open technologies for each step of the workflow. All the materials we have used and produced follow the FAIR principles. In order to carry out our research questions we dealt with two different kinds of materials: the ones directly connected to the software and the ones supporting the structure of the project itself.

Materials directly connected to the software

Firstly, we used as initial material open data from the dataset "Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI" (Peroni, 2021a). This dataset is structured in a two-column CSV file: the first one includes the DOIs of the citing resources retrieved in Crossref, while the second one contains the invalid DOIs of the cited resources. The cited entities were defined as invalid by inspecting the field "reference" in the JSON document returned by querying the Crossref API with the citing DOI, while processing Crossref data for adding open citations in COCI. Since these citations refer to a non-resolvable cited entity, they couldn't be added to COCI.

Additional data is retrieved by the software during its execution: by querying DOI and Crossref API services we retrieve other data about publishers (i.e., their names) from response JSON files. Finally, the output material is a JSON file containing all the data cited above. We opted for JSON file format to store all the data answering the research questions, because this file format allows us to store more heterogeneous information in a more complex and structured way. Indeed, we stored both data directly requested by the original research questions, and those additional data that allow us to have a broader picture on the subject and the research problem. Furthermore, the JSON file format allows us to separate different kinds of data and save also data that is relevant for the graphic representations of our findings but not strictly related to the research questions (e.g. which publishers were involved in citations that were originally invalid and then validated with the DOI API request).

Materials supporting the structure of the project

Since this project has been developed under the FAIR and open principles, we created some structures which are not directly involved in the functioning of the software but rather with the perspective of guaranteeing the reproducibility of the methodological steps, the transparency of the actions and the respect of the standards of the community.

First of all, we created a Data Management Plan (DMP) (Cioffi et al., 2021a), which is a formal document clearly stating how data will be managed during the development of the research project and after its end. As it is good practice, we wrote it down before the beginning of the project and we rearranged it on the basis of the factual necessities that came out during the development of the project. In there, we specified the data we have produced, the access, reuse and preservation policies (Cioffi et al., 2021b). To produce the DMP we used the platform Zenodo, since it guarantees, apart from the aforementioned requirements, interoperability standards (OAI-PMH), to specificate descriptive standard metadata, persistent identifiers for deposited items (e.g. DOI) and authors (e.g. ORCID), integrity and fixity assurance of the deposited items, and finally proper citations to data (Peroni, 2021b).

Then, we produced a Protocol, “Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI” (Cioffi et al., 2021d), whose aim was essentially to crystallize, into a specific sequence of steps, the passages that lead us to undertake the research questions. Similarly to the DMP, we produced multiple versions of the protocol:

1. The first one before the beginning, while thinking about the way in which we wanted to develop the code.
2. A second one after the critiques reported by the peer reviews of our colleagues.
3. The final one after the actual production of the code, where some passages have been changed, and some others deepened.

Furthermore, we created a [web site](#) mainly to visualize the results of this research in a more structured and interactive way. The main objective of having a website is that, in this way, we were able to show in a clear and intuitive way the results we were able to obtain through our project with our software. In the website we proposed the results of our research accompanied or represented by graphical representations. The repository of the site has been created on github, therefore it is freely available and persistent.

Finally we kept four notebooks, one for each of us (which are available in the [GitHub repository of the Open Science course, a.y. 2020/2021](#)). There we annotated the day-by-day work we made in order to carry out our research questions. They can be conceived as a sort of diary that allows the reconstruction of the steps which led us to the project conclusion.

Subjects and methods

The subjects of the current study can be identified as the following:

- a. the **invalid DOIs**, on which we worked in order to understand their validity status and retrieve the information they could provide about the related publishers.
- b. the **publishers** themselves, whose information is retrieved by the DOIs and about which we want to know the number of invalid DOIs they are connected to, either when citing or when cited.

The methods used in carrying out this project are those conceived as compliant with the current Open Science principles. In particular, from the point of view of materials, we used an open dataset as input and produced an open dataset as output as well. Further, in both cases the datasets are stored in non-proprietary file formats: CSV as input and JSON as output.

Secondly, the use of ancillary tools - such as the protocol and the Data Management Plan - and the attention to some specific adroitness - such as commenting on the code, expliciting the licences and adding some files such as `README.md`, `material.md` and `requirements.txt` - allows the reuse and reproducibility of the material we have generated.

Thirdly, we followed the good practices of the field by welcoming peer reviews, critiques, suggestions and trying to improve the work accordingly.

Finally, we maximized knowledge access by using open platforms to store project resources. The output file is also structured to be able to easily extract data that could be used for further analysis on the subject (e.g. the data contained in the list of still invalid citations can be easily reused to recreate a CSV file with the same structure as the one we used as input, in order to rerun the code with this new reduced input in future).

Presentation of the main structure of the code

The software we developed to address the main subjects of our research and all their ancillary aspects follows a structure which aims at being simple, safe and functional, in avoidance of hard coding practices. In particular:

- 1) The **files are semantically divided**, so that all the functions concerning a specific task (e.g.: publisher's identification and related data management) are presented together;
- 2) In order to avoid the necessity to modify data by editing the source code, we structured the software to allow potential future users to **encode information through command-line arguments**, i.e.: the number of processed input CSV lines after which the obtained data are stored to the cache files, the file to be used as input, and the output file. Further, A `README.md` file is provided, which clearly explains how to run the code.
- 3) **Data is periodically stored to specific cache files**, in view of a minimization of the possibility of losing already processed information. The final output file is created with the data stored in the cache files, and in case of a premature interruption of the code run, a specific mechanism allows the computation to restart from the last successfully processed input row.

Figure 1. Simplified overview image of the global structure of our software.

As previously mentioned, the software is organized in files, each of which with a specific functional or semantic purpose:

1. `invalid_dois.py`. This file is the entry point of the whole software, and the main aims of its only function, i.e.: `invalid_dois_main(n, input_csv, output_json)`, are those of:
 - a. Reading the input file,
 - b. Creating the variables where the collected information is temporarily stored,
 - c. Calling the function to keep track of the number of processed lines,
 - d. Calling the function to store the obtained information in the cache files when the number of processed lines from the last write to cache corresponds to the one specified as parameter from the user,
 - e. Checking the current validity state of the citation in examination and storing the information together with its (missed) validation time,
 - f. Calling the functions for the publisher's identification and their related data management. The process is splitted with respect to the validity state of the analysed data, but the alternative steps for validated and non validated citations are specular.
 - g. Calling the function to collect all the data stored in the cache files and use them to fill the output JSON file.
2. `row_number_extractor.py`. This file contains only the function `extract_row_number(publisher_data)`, which exploits the cache files to compute the number of the already successfully processed input rows, so to allow restarting the process only from the first unprocessed line on, in case of unforeseen interruptions of the code run. Its additional aim consists in creating a dictionary for

each publisher in `publisher_data` dictionary, exploiting the data provided in “`publisher_data.csv`”.

3. `csv_writer.py`. The function contained in this file, i.e. `write_to_csv(publisher_data, prefix_to_member_code_dict, external_data_dict, correct_dois_data, incorrect_dois_data)`, limits the possibility of losing the already processed data, by creating cache files and filling them with the data obtained from the parameters it takes in input.
4. `publishers.py`. This file contains all the functions dealing with the identification of the publisher and the management of the related data. In particular, its main functions are `extract_publishers_valid(row, publisher_data, prefix_to_member_code_dict, external_data_dict)`, `extract_publishers_invalid(row, publisher_data, prefix_to_member_code_dict)` and `extract_publishers(prefix, prefix_to_member_code_dict, checking=False)`. More in detail, the latter is aimed at retrieving and storing information about the name, the Crossref member code and the DOI prefix of the publisher of the source identified by a Digital Object Identifier in the dictionary `prefix_to_member_code_dict`. The other two mentioned functions are respectively called when the citational data to analyse has been validated and when it has not. They both manage the addition of unprocessed publishers' dictionaries to `publisher_data` and update the values related to the number of either valid or invalid addressed or received citations, in the case a dictionary for a given publisher already exists. In the case that a publisher's prefix doesn't allow its identification in Crossref, in the version for validated citations only, the function `search_for_publisher_in_other_agencies(row[1], external_data_dict)` is called. The process for the identifications of publishers through external services is explained more in detail in the dedicated following paragraph.
5. `output_creator.py`. Its sole function, `create_output(publisher_data, output_json)`, organizes all the collected data and stores them in the JSON file the user passed as the third parameter of the main function. The purpose of this step is saving the obtained results in view of a maximization of the readability and the reusability of the extracted information.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the software functioning. The entry point function is represented in white, and each colored rectangle represents one of the ancillary functions called in the main one.

Recognition of publishers unknown by Crossref

One thing that we realized while rechecking the validity of previously invalid cited DOIs was that some of the DOIs found valid by the DOI API had prefixes that were not recognized by Crossref. This most likely meant that these prefixes belong to publishers that do not use Crossref as their DOI registration agency. We deemed it valuable to try and find out which publishers these were and which agencies they used to register their DOIs.

For this purpose, we added an extra level of checks for the recently validated DOIs not recognized by Crossref. We send API requests to mEDRA and DataCite (the only registrations agencies other than Crossref to provide an API service at the time this research took place) to try and extract these unidentified publishers. As a last resort and in order to fill the void of an API with a meaningful and relatively fool-proof alternative, if both of the previous agencies failed to recognize the publisher, we check the resolution URL of the article in the response from the DOI API for the existence of a known CNKI URL (CNKI being a widely used agency for Chinese articles) to get a rough estimate of the publishers that are unknown to Crossref but known to CNKI, even though we cannot extract their names.

Output structure

The output file is provided in JSON format for structural reasons. The fields we decided to include are the following:

- a. `citations`, a dictionary with the two fields "valid" and "invalid", each of which includes a list of dictionaries for all the citation data in `correct_dois.csv` and `incorrect_dois.csv` respectively,
- b. `publishers`, a list of dictionaries, each of which contains all information gathered about a publisher extracted from `publisher_data.csv` and `prefix_member_code.json`,
- c. `total_num_of_valid_citations`, an integer showing the number of processed citation data that we found to have been validated after the initial source file creation.
- d. `external_data_for_unrecognized_prefixes`, a dictionary whose fields are dictionaries storing information about those publishers whose prefix didn't lead to an identification in Crossref, and which were consequently identified by external services.

The output was structured in a way which should maximise the reuse of the stored data. For example, the lists of valid and invalid citational data are stored separately because they are conceived to hypothetically serve different scopes, such as -respectively- the direct inclusion in COCI as validated data and a further analysis in a later moment, in order to check whether a currently still invalid citation becomes valid in future. The other output fields are aimed at allowing qualitative and quantitative analysis on the publishers' behaviour trends and on some other overall relevant tendencies.

```
{
  "citations": {
    "valid": [...],
    "invalid": [...]
  },
  "publishers": [...],
  "total_num_of_valid_citations": 15,
  "external_data_for_unrecognized_prefixes": {...}
}
```

Figure 3. Basic structure of the fields of a sample from the output JSON file.

3. Results

Which publishers were responsible (due to their incorrect metadata sent to Crossref) for the missing citations in COCI?

The purpose of this initial part of the work, implicit in this first research question, was to identify not only the names of the publishers responsible for the invalid citations - i.e., the publishers of the valid citing DOIs - but also the total number of citing DOIs for each publisher, both those that remained invalid even after the DOI API request and those that became valid. This distinction may initially appear useless if we consider our sole aim to be analyzing the citational data of the citations that remained invalid even after the DOI API request. However, it seemed useful to keep and incorporate this type of information into data visualizations in order to outline if there are some publishers more than others whose citations in which they appeared as publisher of the citers were then validated.

Starting from the approach of choosing to retrieve this type of additional information as well, the resulting data turned out to be particularly interesting.

Stacked Bar Chart with invalid and valid citing publishers

Figure 4. Number of citing DOIs for first twenty publishers in descending order.

The visualization shown in Figure 4, as well as that provided for the second research question, is built upon the twenty most relevant publishers retrieved in our analysis, with respect to both the number of addressed and received citations. Figure 4 shows several types of interesting information: first, it is noted that there is only one publisher whose number of articles with citing DOIs is significantly greater than all the others, and that is Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health) - more than 370'000. Other significant publishers for the numbers of citing DOIs are: Springer Science and Business Media LLC, Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), Informa UK Limited and Wiley. As for the other publishers, the number of citing DOIs of which they are publishers is between considerably lower figures: between 5000 DOIs and 25000 DOIs approximately. In the second place, at least for what concerns these selected publishers, the number of citing DOIs of now valid citations - after the API requests - is distributed only among a few publishers.

To which publishers did such invalid citations point to (i.e. who published the cited articles)?

As stated in the previous section, in the presentation of the first research question and in the analysis of its data, the visualization for this second research question and the data upon which it is constructed are referring only to the twenty most relevant publishers. The methodology and the approach followed for this part of the research correspond to those declared for the first part, while the citational data we have considered refer to the publishers of the cited articles.

Stacked Bar Chart with invalid and valid cited publishers

Figure 5. Number of cited DOIs for first twenty publishers in descending order.

Figure 2 shows similar results to those shown in Figure 1. Firstly, Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health) is still the publisher with the significantly higher number of DOIs cited than the other publishers (almost 380'000, almost triple the number of the second in the standings). Other significant publishers for the numbers of citing DOIs are: Test accounts, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, Wiley and Elsevier BV. As for the data collected to answer this second research question, the numbers are slightly smaller: around the 380'000 DOIs mentioned for the first publisher, while the number for most of the others is concentrated between 130'000 and 4'000. Secondly, also in this case, the number of DOIs mentioned validated with the API requests are concentrated among a few selected publishers.

How many invalid citations are currently valid?

The aim of this question, i.e. retrieving the total number of currently valid citations, was that of understanding in how many cases the invalidity of the DOIs was due not to the publisher's wrongly provided information to Crossref, but because of external reasons, e.g. because of the lack of information about the cited article, in the moment of the check before the eventual inclusion in COCI. The way through which we obtained this information, was strictly related to the previous two: after making an API request to the DOI server, we kept both the information regarding the citations information and the total number of these citations, obtained with a counter of all these citations.

As the results have pointed out, and as it is shown in the graph above, the actual number of citations validated between the OpenCitations check and the current moment, is quite low. Indeed only 7.7% of the citations have been validated while the remaining data is still invalid. Thus, even if we cannot say with certainty whether the fault for these missing citations is due to the publisher or to other external reasons, these results clearly show that those reasons which invalidated the citations during the COCI check, still persist.

Figure 6. Number and percentages of still invalid citations and now valid citations.

Points of intersection between the first and the second question: the interesting case of self-citations

Comparing the data shown by the visualization shown in Figure 1 with those shown by the visualization shown in Figure 2, it is evident that a lot of publishers are both among the twenty most relevant for citing DOIs and the twenty most relevant for cited DOIs. Through this comparison, another data seems to be relevant: the first publisher is Ovid Technologies in both cases, which stands out as the only publisher to have much greater numbers of DOIs citing or cited than the other considered publishers. In fact, for both the first two research questions' results, we can divide the other publishers into groups, whose values are concentrated around ranges, which are getting wider as the values increase. As the values increase - i.e. the number of DOIs citing or cited - the number of publishers per group defined on the ranges decreases.

These observations from the intersection of the results obtained in answering the research questions cited in the previous sections, we noticed a curious case: some publishers who are among the top twenty citing also appear to be among the top twenty cited in the missing citations in COCI. This fact intrigued us and led us to investigate the matter further to find out if it is a case of self-citation. So we have reworked the data we already have to organize them in order to save the following information: who are the publishers cited by the first ten citing publishers and in what number of citations. To represent the data obtained we have chosen to use a sankey diagram. As the chart shows, some interesting cases that emerge with these data are that of Ovid Technologies, which turns out to be an interesting case of self-citation as we had supposed; but also the case of JSTOR appear as a self-citation case for invalid citations; and finally, the last interesting case is that of Association for Computing Machinery (ACM): most of the invalid citations of which it is the responsible publisher point to

Test accounts, which is a ghost publisher (i.e., not clearly identified) we will talk about in section 4. Discussion.

Figure 7. Sankey diagram to show who the publishers cited by the top 10 cited publishers are (proportionally).

Further results

In addition to the aforementioned results, our algorithm allowed the retrieval of further information, aimed at providing material for further studies on the same topic, qualitative analysis on the retrieved data and future updates of the present research.

Providing Valid and Invalid Citational Data

The obtained output is presented as a JSON file based on three elements. One of these is a dictionary named “citations”, whose function is that of storing as values of the two keys “valid” and “invalid” the lists of respectively validated and still invalid citational data. This structural choice was motivated by the will of providing to the scientific community the possibility of exploiting the two lists for different purposes. In particular, the list stored in the key “valid” is composed of data which could be easily and safely included in COCI index

without the necessity of further checks, since the validity of the cited DOI, which resulted invalid at the time of the creation of the file we used as input, was verified through the process implemented by our software. On the other hand, the list associated with the key “invalid” is composed of citational data which could be profitably exploited in view of further research. In fact, the primary reason why this list of dictionaries is included in the output file is that of providing the possibility to easily convert it into a CSV file to be used as input in a future run of the code. Indeed, the obtained CSV file would represent a reduced version of the one originally used. Accordingly, by repeating the same procedure periodically it would be possible to keep the results updated. In addition to that, these data may be used to qualitatively enrich the analysis on the topic of the publishers’ responsibility. In fact, since they represent a reduced amount of the input data whose invalidity was proven, they could be directly used as input in a software aimed at analysing and correcting the classes of error in Digital Object Identifiers without the need to repeat the API request.

Mapping Publishers and Prefixes

In managing the identification of the publishers, a problem arose with the possibility that publishers were associated with more than one prefix each. For the purposes of our research, the point was handled by locally creating a temporary JSON file to store information about each prefix and the publisher which it identifies (using the publisher’s member code in Crossref), and then using as keys of the `publisher_data` dictionary the strings of the member codes of the publishers instead of their prefixes. However, since we believe that in view of future studies it may be useful to have a mapping between each publisher and all the prefixes it is identified by, a list of prefixes was added to each publisher’s dictionary in `publisher_data`. The main aim in providing this mapping is that of reducing the computational cost of any possible future research by avoiding API requests to identify publishers whose prefixes were already processed.

Tracking Evolutions

Even if for the purposes of our research it was not strictly required, we decided to keep track of the evolutions in the citations’ states by adding to each publisher’s dictionary in `publisher_data` four keys (“responsible_for_v”, “responsible_for_i”, “receiving_v”, “receiving_i”), dividing the data about the citations addressed and received according to their validity state. This choice not only provided an overview on the data trends defined in the time span that occurred between the creation of the original input file (`invalid_dois.csv`) and our software release, but also allowed the computation of ratios and the production of visualizations on the results.

4. Discussion

In general, our research has produced interesting results that clearly lead to an obvious deduction: there are certain publishers that send out a large proportion of the invalid citation data to Crossref. The case is slightly different for the publishers on the receiving side of this problem: even though there are a number of common publishers in our two charts, it is evident that in the receiving chart the most large-scale publishers (Rüdiger, Fleischhacker 2019) are the ones most prone to receiving invalid citations. To showcase this problem, let us use an example: Elsevier is not that high up on the rankings for the responsible publishers (and more than 70% of those citations present in our source file have since been

included in the DOI API and are then not mistakes), but is 5th on the rankings for the receiving publishers, seemingly because of its large number of publications and their vast usage among various fields.

Apart from the basic findings of the research and listing the main responsible/receiving publishers, our study led us to a number of points worth discussing further. One of these points was the relatively large number of invalid citations that have been made to DOIs with invalid prefixes (prefixes not belonging to any publisher in Crossref). We used the umbrella term "unidentified" as the publisher name for all of these DOIs and, as can be seen in the findings section, this "publisher" ranks 8th among the publishers with the most citations received in our source file. However, after closer scrutiny, we can see that around 15% of these received citations are, based on the DOI API, valid citations. This might seem contradictory with the nature of an unidentified publisher, but the most likely culprit in this scenario is that the Crossref data is not as up-to-date as the doi.org data, causing Crossref to not be able to recognize prefixes that in reality do belong to a real publisher.

Another point of interest, which is definitely worth further research but unfortunately out of the scope of this project, is the publisher name "Test accounts" retrieved from the Crossref API for the prefix 10.5555. The name of this hypothetical publisher, the lack of more information about it on Crossref, and the fact that among all the processed data it has only been on the *receiving* part of *strictly invalid* citation data, all point to the conclusion that such a publisher does not exist. In the list of publishers receiving the largest number of invalid citations, "Test accounts" ranks second with more than 17000 invalid citations pointing to it.

For a select number of publishers responsible for the most invalid citation data, the number for invalid citation data received is also very high, surprisingly suggesting that these publishers have been self-citing with invalid (or at least, still not yet validated) citation data. The main publisher of this type is Ovid Technologies, which, in spite of being of a much smaller size and importance of publishers such as Elsevier or Springer, leads the responsible for invalid citation list by a huge margin. Though out of the scope of this project, the real reasons behind this incident are definitely worth studying in further research. Our deduction based on available sources is that this invalid self-citation might be caused by using internal DOI data not yet available to the public and Crossref.

Future evolutions

In the original purposes of the present research project, the work on DOIs was supposed to be limited to their validation through a REST API service. However, thanks to the received reviews of our protocol (Massari, 2021; Tural, 2021), we started conceiving a possible extension of our software with a mechanism of correction of the DOIs which result to be still invalid after the Rest API validation attempt. In particular, following a suggestion proposed by Arcangelo Massari in the aforementioned review (Massari, 2021), this purpose could be achieved by exploiting the algorithm for error classification and correction (Boente et al., 2021) projected by our colleagues. As we stated in *Rebuttal letter to reviewers of "Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI" (Version 2)* (Cioffi et al., 2021c), we believe that this integration might represent a significant added value for the following reasons:

1. It could allow the identification of the publishers which would be otherwise excluded from our results because of an error in the prefix of the cited DOI of a given publication, since the mechanism we rely on for the publishers' retrieval is based on

their identification throughout a request to a dedicated Crossref API service which exploits DOIs' prefixes.

2. It may provide some qualitative information about the reasons why some citational data were invalid at the time of the creation of the original input file, i.e. : "invalid_dois.csv".
3. As an effect of the previous two points, it could enhance the quality of the results of our primary aim research both qualitatively and quantitatively.
4. It would implement an effective collaboration among the authors of two projects which are profitably conceivable as complementary.

With respect to the publishers' responsibility attributions, expliciting a distinction between the DOIs validated at the first check through a DOI API service from the ones validated only after the correction could be useful. Indeed, the division may provide valuable material for qualitative studies on possible trends of DOIs' invalidity reasons for each publisher.

5. Conclusions

The research questions have been broadly answered by the result data provided by the publishers-retrieving-software. Indeed, the results have shown three major points. The former is that only a few publishers have a high number of invalid citations, of resources either citing or cited, while most of the remaining publishers flattens around small values. The second one shows that only a small part of the previously invalid citations have successively become valid, and that, therefore, the issues that characterized the previously invalid DOIs are still present. Thirdly, some, relevant, publishers are involved in invalid self-citations, such as Ovid Technologies and JSTOR.

The results of the project could be applied to the more general research area of COCI and OpenCitations, as well as the other projects that deal with open citational data. Indeed, this could make sure that more data can be integrated into COCI by grasping the issue of invalid DOIs at the root, therefore not correcting the invalid DOIs already collected, but correcting the activities carried out by the publishers that lead to these missing citations and invalid data; or hypothesize a different method of collecting the citational data from publishers that can prevent the insertion of incorrect citational data in platforms such as Crossref. Further improvements, concerning the recognition and correction of the errors affecting the prefixes, may lead to a broader comprehension of the world of the publishers related to the invalid DOIs, by adding to the research all the DOIs that, for this reason, could not be inserted in the final computations.

References

- Alessia Cioffi, Sara Coppini, Arianna Moretti, & Nooshin Shahidzadeh. (2021). Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI - Protocol V.4. [10.17504/protocols.io.bv9jn94n](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bv9jn94n)
- Alexiou, G., Vahdati, S., Lange, C., Papastefanatos, G., & Lohmann, S. (2016). OpenAIRE LOD Services: Scholarly Communication Data as Linked Data. In A. González-Beltrán, F. Osborne, & S. Peroni (Eds.), *Semantics, Analytics, Visualization. Enhancing Scholarly Data* (Vol. 9792, pp. 45–50). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53637-8_6
- Bagnacani, A., Ciancarini, P., Di Iorio, A., Nuzzolese, A. G., Peroni, S., & Vitali, F. (2015). The Semantic Lancet Project: A Linked Open Dataset for Scholarly Publishing. In P. Lambrix, E. Hyvönen, E. Blomqvist, V. Presutti, G. Qi, U. Sattler, Y. Ding, & C. Ghidini (Eds.), *Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management* (Vol. 8982, pp. 101–105). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-17966-7_10
- Blomqvist, E., Ding, Y., Ghidini, C., Hyvönen, E., Lambrix, P., Presutti, V., Qi, G., & Sattler, U. (Eds.). (2015). *Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management: EKAW 2014 Satellite Events, VISUAL, EKM1, and ARCOE-Logic*, Linköping, Sweden, November 24-28, 2014. Revised Selected Papers (1st ed. 2015). Springer International Publishing : Imprint: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-17966-7>
- Boente, R. (2021). Review of: 'DMP Investigating Missing Citations in COCI (zenodo.4671487)'. Qeios. <https://doi.org/10.32388/T0UF3H>
- Boudry, C., & Chartron, G. (2017). Availability of digital object identifiers in publications archived by PubMed. *Scientometrics*, 110(3), 1453–1469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2225-6>
- Cioffi, Alessia, Coppini, Sara, Moretti, Arianna, & Shahidzadeh Asadi, Nooshin. (2021). Investigating Missing Citations in COCI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4671486>
- Cioffi, Alessia, Coppini, Sara, Shahidzadeh Asadi, Nooshin, & Moretti, Arianna. (2021). Rebuttal letter to reviewers of 'Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI'. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4725899>
- Cioffi, Alessia, Shahidzadeh Asadi, Nooshin, Moretti, A., & Coppini, Sara. (n.d.). Investigating missing DOIs [Web site]. <https://open-sci.github.io/2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code/>
- Cortez, E., da Silva, A. S., Gonçalves, M. A., Mesquita, F., & de Moura, E. S. (2007). FLUX-CIM: Flexible unsupervised extraction of citation metadata. *Proceedings of the 2007 Conference on Digital Libraries - JCDL '07*, 215. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1255175.1255219>
- Franceschini, F., Maisano, D., & Mastrogiacomo, L. (2014). Scientific journal publishers and omitted citations in bibliometric databases: Any relationship? *Journal of Informetrics*, 8(3), 751–765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2014.07.003>
- Franceschini, F., Maisano, D., & Mastrogiacomo, L. (2015). Errors in DOI indexing by bibliometric databases. *Scientometrics*, 102(3), 2181–2186. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1503-4>
- Garcia, A., Lopez, F., Garcia, L., Giraldo, O., Bucheli, V., & Dumontier, M. (2018). Biotea: Semantics for Pubmed Central. *PeerJ*, 6, e4201. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4201>

- González-Beltrán, A., Osborne, F., & Peroni, S. (Eds.). (2016). *Semantics, Analytics, Visualization. Enhancing Scholarly Data: Second International Workshop, SAVE-SD 2016*, Montreal, QC, Canada, April 11, 2016, Revised Selected Papers (1st ed. 2016). Springer International Publishing : Imprint: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53637-8>
- Heibi, I. (2019). COCI, the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3502870>
- Heibi, I., Peroni, S., & David, S. (2019). Crowdsourcing open citations with CROCI - An analysis of the current status of open citations, and a proposal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3384729>
- Heibi, I., Peroni, S., & Shotton, D. (2019). Software review: COCI, the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations. *Scientometrics*, 121(2), 1213–1228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03217-6>
- Hutchins, B. I., Baker, K. L., Davis, M. T., Diwersy, M. A., Haque, E., Harriman, R. M., Hoppe, T. A., Leicht, S. A., Meyer, P., & Santangelo, G. M. (2019). The NIH Open Citation Collection: A public access, broad coverage resource. *PLOS Biology*, 17(10), e3000385. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000385>
- Jiang, Z., & Liu, X. (2013). Recovering missing citations in a scholarly network: A 2-step citation analysis to estimate publication importance. *Proceedings of the 13th ACM/IEEE-CS Joint Conference on Digital Libraries - JCDL '13*, 419. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2467696.2467782>
- Martín-Martín, A., Thelwall, M., Orduna-Malea, E., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2021). Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, Scopus, Dimensions, Web of Science, and OpenCitations' COCI: A multidisciplinary comparison of coverage via citations. *Scientometrics*, 126(1), 871–906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03690-4>
- Massari, A. (2021). Review of: 'Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI'. *Qeios*. <https://doi.org/10.32388/X2DX81>
- Pentz, E. (2001). CrossRef: The missing link. *College & Research Libraries News*, 62(2), 206–228. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.62.2.206>
- Peroni, S. (2019). OpenCitations: Current Developments. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.2598780>
- Peroni, Silvio. (2021a). Data Management Plan. https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1NabMeG_OAxv6AoBLvHMTO0jMPXYSqznkvud7D0Jjg1k/edit#slide=id.gabac78ff03_0_0
- Peroni, Silvio. (2021b). Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4625300>
- Santini, C. (2021). Review of: 'Investigating Missing Citations in COCI (1.0)'. *Qeios*. <https://doi.org/10.32388/DIA06O>
- Sara Coppini, Arianna Moretti, Nooshin Shahidzadeh, & Alessia Cioffi. (2021). *open-sci/2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code: Version 1.1.0 (v1.1.0)* [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5070140>

Schubotz, M., Krämer, L., Meuschke, N., Hamborg, F., & Gipp, B. (2017). Evaluating and Improving the Extraction of Mathematical Identifier Definitions. In G. J. F. Jones, S. Lawless, J. Gonzalo, L. Kelly, L. Goeriot, T. Mandl, L. Cappellato, & N. Ferro (Eds.), *Experimental IR Meets Multilinguality, Multimodality, and Interaction* (Vol. 10456, pp. 82–94). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65813-1_7

Tural, D. (2021). Review of: 'Investigating Invalid DOIs in COCI v1 (protocols.io.bt5xnq7n)'. *Qeios*. <https://doi.org/10.32388/WHWOI8>

Williams, K., Wu, J., Choudhury, S. R., Khabsa, M., & Giles, C. L. (2014). Scholarly big data information extraction and integration in the CiteSeer[®] digital library. 2014 IEEE 30th International Conference on Data Engineering Workshops, 68–73. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDEW.2014.6818305>

Zhu, J., Hu, G., & Liu, W. (2019). DOI errors and possible solutions for Web of Science. *Scientometrics*, 118(2), 709–718. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2980-7>